

Path2Integrity questionnaire for students with an academic degree and researchers (graduates)

Instructions

During this evaluation, we kindly ask you to respond to the following case scenarios about research practices. Each case scenario starts with a short description followed by 4 steps which build on one another. Only one option can be chosen for each question.

First decide which action is in line with good research practices and then use the slider to indicate how confident you feel about your answer.

Please choose a reason for your answer by choosing the option that best suits your opinion and then use the slider to indicate how confident you feel about your answer.

Please note that you cannot return to a previous page of the survey! But you may always skip a question, stop the survey, or withdraw from it completely.

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(Path2Integrity questionnaire for students without an academic degree (undergraduates))

